

Government incentivization of partnerships in South Africa

An audit of THRIP and the Innovation Fund

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Abstract: *Worldwide, innovation policy is perceived to be at the heart of economic growth and global competitiveness, and nations invest vast amounts of money to give effect to innovation. Higher education institutions, in partnership with industry, are expected to play a key role in supporting the national system of innovation and developing the nation's global competitiveness. This paper draws on the audit of higher education–industry partnerships conducted by the Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC) of South Africa during 2002–03. It plots the South African government's programme of incentives for industry–higher education partnerships through two funding programmes: the Technology and Human Resources for Industry Programme (THRIP) and the Innovation Fund. It argues that, notwithstanding considerable outputs, such as publications, patents/artefacts and the involvement of postgraduate students, it is vital that the incentivization of higher education–industry partnerships is managed in such a way that past relations of inequality among higher education institutions and in the broader society are not reproduced.*

Keywords: *HE–industry partnerships; innovation; global competitiveness; THRIP; Innovation Fund; South Africa*

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The need to encourage and support partnerships between higher education institutions (HEIs), industry, and state science, engineering and technology (SET) institutions in South Africa cannot be overemphasized. Innovation policy is perceived to be at the heart of initiatives to enhance economic policy. It has been argued that in South Africa there is a 'symbolic' rather

than a 'substantive' policy expectation that higher education institutions should be responsive to national socio-economic priorities (Kruss, 2002). It is believed that they should play a pivotal role in developing the country's global competitiveness and be more proactive in facilitating access to higher education opportunities for the majority of blacks and women who were

previously marginalized by *apartheid* policies. Indeed the National Commission on Higher Education (NCHE) (1996) is explicit that 'higher education should take seriously the problems and challenges presented by the societal context in which it operates'. In the South African higher education policy context, the NCHE uses the term 'responsiveness' to suggest a shift to a more open and interactive higher education system that responds to the social, cultural, political and economic needs of its environment and adapts itself to changes in that environment. Concomitantly, higher education institutions in South Africa are expected to lead the process of redress to past socio-economic inequities and inequalities.

Castells (1996) argues that improvement in national competitiveness is increasingly dependent on the complex interaction between historically rooted political institutions and globalized economic agents. He refers to increased 'networking' between organizations within the seemingly paradoxical paradigm of competition and collaboration, and argues that organizations in different sectors are beginning to see the benefits of working collaboratively rather than in isolation in order to increase the efficiency, quality and quantity of outputs.

Against this backdrop, this paper draws on the audit of one form of higher education–industry partnership conducted by the Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC) of South Africa during the period 2002–03 (HSRC, 2003).¹ It reports on the scale of government incentivization of higher education–industry partnerships in three innovation bands – information and communications technology (ICT), biotechnology and new materials development. The HSRC study focuses on the Technology and Human Resources for Industry Programme (THRIP) and the Innovation Fund, both government funding programmes. The following section introduces these two funding programmes and comments briefly on their role in fostering collaboration among industry, higher education institutions, and SET institutions (SETIs).

It should be mentioned at the outset that, while the two funding programmes are housed at South Africa's National Research Foundation (NRF) and have channelled substantial funds towards promoting higher education–industry partnerships, their missions and foci are different. THRIP is oriented towards capacity building: its main aim is 'to produce a flow of highly skilled researchers and technology managers who understand research, technology development and the diffusion of technology from the viewpoints of both industry and academia' (THRIP, 2002a, p 2). The Innovation Fund, on the other hand, seeks to promote technological innovation and transdisciplinary

collaboration within the research community by encouraging and supporting longer-term, large-scale, collaborative innovation projects in the higher education sector, government science councils, civil society and the private sector.

In the remainder of the paper I examine the nature and volume of higher education–industry partnerships supported by THRIP and the Innovation Fund, highlight key differences in the ways that THRIP and the Innovation Fund incentivize partnerships, and argue that if the sensitive issues of equity and the redress of past inequities are not fully addressed in the process of pursuing higher education–industry partnerships, the incentivization initiative runs the risk of reproducing past relations of inequality.

THRIP and the Innovation Fund

THRIP

The Technology and Human Resources for Industry Programme is a funding programme managed by the National Research Foundation on behalf of South Africa's Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). Its purpose is to support scientific research, technology development and technology diffusion activities and to improve South African industry's competitiveness (DTI, 1998). Launched in 1991, it is funded by the DTI and managed by the NRF. Its primary objectives are to:

- increase the number and quality of people with appropriate skills for the development and management of technology for industry;
- promote increased interaction among researchers and technology managers in industry, higher education and state science, engineering and technology institutions, with the aim of developing skills for the commercial exploitation of science and technology; and
- stimulate industry and government to increase their investment in research, technology development, technology diffusion and the promotion of innovation.

THRIP (1997, p 7) itself contends that a major stimulus for its establishment was the serious concern over the quality and quantity of engineering graduates in South Africa. The concerns were reflected in reports by the South African Engineering Association and the government's Economic Advisory Council. They focused on three key areas, namely:

- the development of high-level personnel;
- the expansion and improvement of engineering education in the tertiary sector; and

- increases in academic salaries to market-related levels in order to attract and retain able engineering academics in higher education institutions (THRIP, 1997, p 8).

In the context of a democratic and rapidly transforming South African society, issues of redressing past inequities, access to opportunities for the previously excluded black majority, and representation in the area of knowledge generation and dissemination continue to be high on the agenda of policy makers. In this regard, at the heart of THRIP's strategic priorities is its capacity-building mission. THRIP's main aim is 'to produce a flow of highly skilled researchers and technology managers who understand research, technology development and the diffusion of technology from the viewpoints of both industry and academia' (THRIP, 2002a, p 2). To that end THRIP strives to support an increase in the number and quality of black and female graduates who intend to pursue careers in science, engineering and technology. It also promotes technological know-how in small, medium-sized and micro-enterprises (SMMEs) through the deployment of skills vested in higher education institutions and SETIs. Finally, it facilitates and supports projects in which multiple firms collaborate and share in the project outcomes.

One of THRIP's flagship programmes for realizing the above goals is the Technology Innovation Promotion through the Transfer of People (TIPTOP). THRIP (2002b, p 8) argues that TIPTOP 'represents a set of placement mechanisms to promote mobility of people participating in THRIP projects among the organizations involved in the projects (HEIs, SETIs, and industrial laboratories)'. TIPTOP has four options for facilitating the placement of people participating in THRIP projects:

- *Option 1* involves the exchange of researchers and technology managers between HEIs, SETIs and industry. THRIP provides support for academic researchers in HEIs to work in industrial laboratories for a predetermined period. Reciprocally, THRIP industrial researchers and technology managers are temporarily seconded to HEIs and SETIs to conduct research of direct relevance to the industry involved.
- *Option 2* involves the placement of science, engineering and technology graduates in industry while they are working towards a higher degree in a joint research project. The placed graduates are assigned a mentor in the firm and are supported on a contract basis for a fixed period to work on THRIP-approved research or technology development projects in the firms.

- *Option 3* deals exclusively with the placement of graduates in SMMEs for a maximum of two years to work on THRIP-approved research or technology development projects. Graduates in this option are not expected to be enrolled for a higher degree, but THRIP's secretariat facilitates and monitors their supervision.
- *Option 4* supports the secondment of SET-skilled company employees in HEIs or SETIs to do research within THRIP projects while studying towards a higher degree. The secondment is for a maximum of two years for a Master's degree and three years for a doctoral degree.

Innovation Fund

The Innovation Fund started in the Department of Arts, Culture, Science and Technology (DACST)² for a trial period in financial year 1997/98. While the initial area of concentration was crime prevention (HSRC, 2003, p 21), the Innovation Fund has since grown in size, shape and focus. Its key objectives are now to:

- promote technological innovation in the research community;
- permit reallocation of funds towards the key issues of competitiveness, quality of life, environmental sustainability and the harnessing of information technology;
- increase the extent to which funds for the activities of government SETIs are obtained via competitive processes; and
- promote transdisciplinary collaboration across sectors in South Africa.

An interview with the Director of the Innovation Fund elicited several additions to the programme's objectives:

- it strives to encourage and support longer-term, large-scale collaborative innovation projects in the higher education sector, government science councils, civil society and the private sector;
- it promotes increased networking and cross-sectoral collaboration within South Africa's national innovation system;
- it encourages close relationships between those conducting the research activities and those who will be expected to make practical use of the results; and
- it facilitates the financing of problem-oriented research involving participants from many disciplines.

Given that many countries regard innovation as central to economic growth and global competitiveness, the Innovation Fund is seen as governmental investment

that gives effect to this concept (Berger, 2003, p 524). Like THRIP, the Innovation Fund is also managed by the NRF and directs large grants to consortia of researchers. However, unlike THRIP, whose main focus is capacity building, the Innovation Fund's focus is on final-stage research projects in which knowledge is translated into new or improved products, productivity processes and services. Berger notes that the Innovation Fund assists in the conversion of research ideas into commercially useful end products by funding essential items such as equipment, R&D expertise, access to managerial skills, the securing of intellectual property rights and the construction of prototypes. The Innovation Fund is thus a policy instrument for leveraging economic and social resources. It strives to address South Africa's socio-economic challenges by harnessing science and technology competencies to develop and maintain cutting-edge global competitiveness.

In the following section an outline is provided of the nature and volume of partnerships among industry, HEIs and science and technology institutions that were incentivized through funding by THRIP and the Innovation Fund. The database covers THRIP partnerships for 2001–02 and all Innovation Fund projects since its inception in 1996 up to 2002.

Nature and volume of incentivized partnerships

The HSRC audit identified a total of 423 industry–higher education–SETI partnerships that had been incentivized through THRIP and the Innovation Fund. Of these, 186 were in the three critical bands of ICT, biotechnology and new materials development. Other innovation-related partnerships were found in forestry, agriculture, minerals, power, manufacturing, animal husbandry and crime prevention.

Of the 186 government-funded partnerships in the three critical bands of ICT, biotechnology and new materials development, 66 (35%) were in biotechnology, 53 (28%) were in ICT and 67 (37%) were in new materials development (see Figure 1).

THRIP supported 87% of the partnerships, while the Innovation Fund supported 13%. This apparently skewed percentage is largely due to the nature of the two funding programmes. The Innovation Fund targets relatively large, final-stage research projects with a minimum value of ZAR1 million compared to THRIP's minimum per-project value of ZAR200,000. The average expenditure per project for the Innovation Fund is ZAR5.4 million per year, while the average expenditure for THRIP is ZAR1.5 million per year (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Breakdown of Innovation Fund and THRIP projects by three critical technological bands. Source: HSRC (2003).

Figure 2. Average cost per project for Innovation Fund and THRIP. Source: HSRC (2003).

THRIP and the Innovation Fund invested just over ZAR869 million on industry–higher education–SETI partnerships. THRIP's share of this investment was ZAR559 million (64%), while the Innovation Fund's share was ZAR307 million (36%).

Given the scale of government investment in the promotion of collaboration, capacity building, technology diffusion and the promotion of innovation, it becomes pertinent to examine the outcomes of these two programmes.

Outputs of incentivization programmes

THRIP and the Innovation Fund have set themselves lofty yet pertinent goals for enhancing scientific and innovative inclinations while at the same time responding to the country's priorities in the areas of economic growth, employment growth and social development. Given the differing missions and goals of the two programmes, it is not surprising to discover

differences in each programme's funding focus. For instance, THRIP tends to fund more partnerships with universities, while the Innovation Fund tends to support projects in the SETIs. Out of the THRIP budget of ZAR559.4 million, for example, ZAR421.3 million (75%) were allocated to universities, ZAR104.3 million (19%) to SETIs and ZAR33.9 million (6%) to technikons (see Figure 3).³ The opposite is the case with the Innovation Fund. In 2002 and 2003, ZAR221.5 million (72%) of its ZAR309.6 million budget were allocated to SETIs and ZAR88.2 million (28%) were allocated to universities (see Figure 4).

It can be reasonably concluded that THRIP and the Innovation Fund have made a marked financial contribution towards the incentivization of higher education–industry linkages. Collectively, THRIP and the Innovation Fund have supported 573 industry partners, many of which were involved in two or more

Figure 3. Expenditure by institutional type for THRIP-funded projects.

Source: HSRC (2003).

Figure 4. Expenditure by institutional type for Innovation Fund projects.

Source: HSRC (2003).

projects, with some involved in as many as eleven. Forty-one HEIs and SETIs were the primary beneficiaries of THRIP and Innovation Fund support. One of the programmes' most marked achievements is the changed attitude of industry, which now treats its relationships with HEIs as collaborative partnerships in which there is a commitment to a common set of goals and overall objectives rather than a mere 'business arrangement'. Industry's motives for engaging in partnership are now 'linked to issues such as access to research facilities and expertise and to human resource development, rather than just narrow motives of financial gain and increased competitiveness' (HSRC, 2003, p 127).

What then is the extent of the 'outputs' of the incentivization programmes? The study conceived of outputs as research publications, products or artefacts, patents and the involvement of postgraduate students in research projects for the purpose of gaining research experience in the designated technology bands.

THRIP projects produced 719 publications, while Innovation Fund projects produced 166. In terms of patents and artefacts, THRIP produced 15 while the Innovation Fund generated 78. THRIP produced 143 products while the Innovation Fund produced 60. Regarding postgraduate research, 997 students were involved in THRIP research projects, while 296 were involved in research projects supported by the Innovation Fund. Again, the different emphasis evident in the forms of output – whether patents, artefacts, publications or students – reflects the specific aims of each programme.

Notwithstanding these achievements, it is important not to lose sight of the sensitive issues of equity and redress. It is vital that the incentivization of higher education–industry partnerships is managed in such a way that past relations of inequality among HEIs and in the broader society are not reproduced. The recipients of THRIP research funds, for example, continue to be predominantly traditionally white, advantaged, urban-based universities. These are institutions that have enduring traditions of research and privileged access to financial resources from the state (see Figure 5). This has serious implications for THRIP's priority of providing incentives for the training of an increased number of blacks and females in the fields of science, engineering and technology, and for promoting research capacity building in technikons and historically black universities (THRIP, 1998, 2003).

Indeed, THRIP (2002a, p 16) acknowledges that it has failed to satisfy its priority target with respect to the participation of historically black universities. In the context of South Africa's higher education sector, historically black universities are also known as historically disadvantaged institutions. Except for the

Figure 5. Expenditure for THRIP and Innovation Fund projects by HEI.
 Source: HSRC (2003).

University of Fort Hare – which was founded in 1916 and was for many years the only institution in the whole of Southern Africa providing higher education opportunities to blacks (Morrow and Gxabalashé, 2000; Maaba, 2001; Morrow, 2002) – the other historically black universities were established only in the 1970s and 1980s. The author’s contention is that THRIP’s support for research with respect to increasing the number of black and female researchers in science and technology fields, and to promoting research capacity building in historically black universities and technikons, needs to be opened for further discussion *vis-à-vis* its capacity-building mandate.

THRIP (2002a) argues that HEIs have been able to undertake research that they otherwise could not have done, that they now attract and retain more students and that researchers have been encouraged to interact with business, effectively changing the institutional culture. THRIP also believes that it has performed well in terms of its objective of increasing SMME participation, considering that a significant number (possibly 60%) of the SMMEs participating in THRIP are spin-offs from higher education institutions.

While we recognize the validity of these points, it should not be forgotten that more than 75% of THRIP’s allocation for research largely benefits the Universities of Stellenbosch, Cape Town, Pretoria, Natal, Potchefstroom and the Witwatersrand (see Figure 5). These are traditionally white, advantaged, urban-based universities with an established culture of research as well as a history of privilege. While the remaining funding is fairly widely distributed, technikons (both historically advantaged and historically disadvantaged) receive only 6% of the total expenditure, while historically black universities receive only 4% of expenditure. In its latest strategic plan, THRIP (2003, p 11) acknowledges that ‘participation by historically black universities (HBUs) remains very low and has in fact fallen in both absolute and relative terms’. THRIP (2002a, p vi) acknowledges that its inability ‘to attract significant numbers of projects from historically black universities was significant’. However, it also notes that ‘the rising participation of black students against this background reflects increases in the numbers of black students at historically white institutions (HWI)’ (THRIP, 2002a, p 16).

The disparities in the allocation of research funds between traditionally white, advantaged universities and historically black, disadvantaged universities are a clear indication of the latter's lack of capacity for research. With the exception of the University of Durban Westville and the University of the Western Cape,⁴ which compete reasonably well for research funds with some of the advantaged institutions at the lower end of the scale, only two rural-based historically black universities – the University of the North and the University of Fort Hare – received substantial amounts of funding, but these were still well below the average half-a-million Rand mark. Other rural-based historically black institutions – the Universities of the North West, Transkei, Venda and Zululand – did not receive any direct funding for projects although they participated in research teams with other universities in one or more of the technology bands.

The highest beneficiary of THRIP research allocation, the University of Stellenbosch, received ZAR129,446,558, while other advantaged universities received research funds in the region of eight-digit figures (see Figure 5).

The poor performance of the historically black universities can be attributed largely to the purpose for which they initially established. Bunting (2002, p 74) argues that historically black universities were not established because of an academic need. On the contrary, their establishment was overtly political and instrumental – political in that their existence played a role in the maintenance of the overall *apartheid* socio-political agenda, and instrumental because they were established to train black people who would be useful to the *apartheid* state. Thus most historically black universities do not have a strong culture of research. Cloete and Fehnel (2002, p 395) agree that historically black universities were never intended, nor equipped, to become strong academic and research institutions. Thaver (2003) expresses concern that, when one combines the academic staffing profile of some universities with that of research outputs, a racially skewed picture emerges. She worries that this shows a severe distortion in the potential for knowledge production.

That said, however, all is not doom and gloom. Telkom's Centres of Excellence (CoEs) programme – which is a joint effort between Telkom, the telecommunications industry and government – is a funding and research collaboration that seeks to promote research in communications technology and allied social sciences. Valued at ZAR150 million and backed by bursaries to support 200 postgraduate students in communications technologies, it is being touted as an example that can be replicated in other

countries to increase the number of graduates entering the telecom job pool (Stones, 2003). There are currently fourteen Telkom Centres of Excellence in HEIs, including the Universities of Durban Westville, KwaZulu-Natal, Fort Hare, Port Elizabeth, Pretoria, North, Rhodes, Western Cape, and Technikons Pretoria, Northern Gauteng, North West and M.L. Sultan.

Summary

Many countries regard innovation as crucial to economic growth and global competitiveness. They invest vast amounts of money to give effect to that concept. The South African government's incentivization of industry–higher education partnerships through THRIP and the Innovation Fund is one among many programmes created to support the country's national system of innovation. This article has drawn on the audit of higher education–industry partnerships conducted by the Human Sciences Research Council during 2002–03 to sketch some aspects of the incentivization of partnerships among industry, HEIs and SETIs. It has described the key objectives and missions of THRIP and the Innovation Fund in relation to providing additional incentives for increasing the number of black and female researchers wishing to pursue careers in SET fields, promoting research capacity building in historically black universities and all technikons, stimulating technological innovation in the research community and promoting technology diffusion.

The article then sketched the considerable outputs of the government incentivization of partnerships. A total of 1,293 postgraduate students were involved with research teams in which 885 publications, 83 patents/artefacts and 203 products had been produced. However, notwithstanding these commendable gains, the allocation of research funds, in particular by THRIP, continues to favour traditionally white, advantaged, urban-based universities with long traditions of research and accompanying investment. It is argued that this does not augur well for THRIP's mission to increase the number of black and female researchers in SET fields and to contribute towards research capacity building in historically black institutions. In a young democracy such as South Africa, it may distort the potential for knowledge production.

Notes

¹Unless otherwise stated, statistics and other findings cited in this article are from the HSRC study, as reported in HSRC (2003).

²In 2004 DACST was divided into two separate Departments – the Department of Arts and Culture and the Department of Science and Technology.

³The institutional type known as 'technikon' in the context of South Africa's higher education sector is equivalent to a European polytechnic. As a result of the merger process currently underway in South Africa's HEIs, technikons are now known as 'universities of technology'.

⁴While these two universities are also historically black universities, they are not located in rural and poor former *apartheid* 'homelands', but in the urban areas of Durban and Cape Town.

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